

WHAT IS REINCARNATE

Reincarnate aims at advancing circular economy practices within the European construction industry and enabling to significantly maximise the life cycle of buildings, construction products and materials, reduce CDW by 80%, increase the reusability of buildings, construction products and materials and, as a result, lower the sector's emissions by 70%.

KEY FACTS

Demo Case / Value Chain

Inventory of the material bank, Teknikhögden, Stockholm

Lead Partners

Ragn-Sells, Akademiska Hus, DEMO Consultants, TU-Berlin

Innovation(s) applied

BIM for Circular Value Flow planning

TRL (before → after)

3 → 6

Related Deliverables

D1.1, D1.3, D1.4

CONTEXT AND INNOVATION

The innovation BIM for circular value flow planning (BIM-CVFP) builds on the concept of Circular value flow planning (CVFP). The aim is to enable better planning of material flows and thus enable circular material flows and keeping material at a high quality in the industrial system as long and qualitative as possible. BIM for circular value flow planning is enabled by using a BIM model as the facilitator of data collected from the built environment to estimate the amount of material as well as the material quality and by doing so, enable decision making for increased circularity. Ragn-Sells is demonstrating the innovation by testing how flat glass from windows are recycled to new flat glass for windows. The demo “flat glass to flat glass” shows the end of that circle while the demonstration “inventory of the material bank”, demonstrates the initiating phase of the innovation.

In the demonstration “inventory of the material bank” we explore methods for data collection and how the collected data can be enriched in a BIM-model. We look at a scenario where a BIM-model exists as well as a scenario where a BIM-model needs to be created using a 3D scan and point cloud conversion.

Once data is collected and applied in the CP-IM platform, the CVFP module suggests what materials can be recycled, and which needs to be downgraded or sent to landfill.

TECHNICAL HIGHLIGHTS

- Core technologies or methods
- Data sources and processing steps
- Integration with CP-IM (modules, APIs)
- Lessons learned or observed benefits

DEMONSTRATION AND RESULTS

Together with Akademiska Hus (property owner), we identified a building that was suitable for demonstrating the inventory part of the circular value flow planning module (CVFP). The building chosen for the demo case was Teknikhögden, a building from the 1960s that was scheduled for demolition. The inventory was delimited to windows which made it easier to focus the work and connect to D1.1 which outlines the digital ontology for flat glass. The ontology can be used to develop the CVFP module.

First, we did a 3D laser scanning to get a point cloud, for the purpose to generate a BIM model of the building. With the scanning software we created a point of interest (POI) structure connected to the quality control for flat glass recycling to transfer the data to the BIM model.

After that we did a manual inventory of the windows in the building to identify, and quality assure which windows were suitable for recycling and which were better suited for downcycling or landfill. That information was connected to the ontology from D1.1 and shared within CP-IM as well as connected to the POI structure. There was a previous BIM-model available which was used to compare different scenarios for an inventory and transfer data to the CP-IM platform. Transfer data from manual quality assurance by using digital software (POI structure) for the creation of a BIM model is an efficient way to add information in different stages of the building lifecycle.

In general, it was very efficient to use the CP-IM platform and enrich the old BIM model with window quality as well as estimating the amount of glass that could be extracted for recycling compared to a manual process.

If there is no BIM-model, the process of creating one using a laser scan and point cloud is time consuming but once the BIM-model is available it can be enriched using CP-IM or manually enriched with the glass quality data which then enables calculations of the amount of glass available for recycling, reuse or detoxification. Note that when the BIM model is created other data than glass can be added by other actors that use the CI-IM platform.

KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

KPI	Baseline	Expected / Achieved
An inventory together with a 3D scanning is a more efficient way of making inventories of the built environment and gives higher accuracy.	For teknikhögden (2200m ²) a manual inventory would take ~ 2 days with limited possibility to quality control any measurement data without going back into the building.	If there is no BIM model and that needs to be created. It might be more efficient (in terms of calendar time) to just do a manual inventory. However, just a manual inventory will make it difficult to share the information in a value-creating way with multiple actors
It is more time efficient to do an inventory using CP-IM compared to a manual inventory.	Same as above	1 floor plan took 20 min and all of the building at Teknikhögden took 4h.
A scanning can facilitate all relevant geometries and information to create a BIM model based on the scanning.	No baseline	Yes, assuming that there are no hidden parts in the building that are to be part of the BIM model. Different scanning methods give different data granularity.
Can the data points collected in the inventory be shared in a scalable way using the CP-IM platform?	No baseline	Yes

The different methods yielded the following estimates.

METHOD	Glass – Recyclable (kg)	Glass – Downgrade (kg)	Est. CO2 savings (kg)
Initial guess	3105	N/A	1646
Manual inventory	3887	22	2060
3D scan	4096	22	2171
3D & LiDAR	5148	22	2728

The estimates will be compared to the actual output of the production process in the demonstration “flat glass to flat glass”.

IMPACTS AND REPLICATION

CATEGORY	IMPACTS	FOCUS	CONTRIBUTION LEVEL
Scientific	I1-I6	Knowledge creation, CP-IM data models, predictive methods	Low
Societal	I7-I12	Training, awareness, stakeholder engagement	High
Techno-economic	I13-I18	New value chains, digital tools, replication potential	High

REPLICATION POTENTIAL

There is potential to repeat and further develop the demonstration in future demolition projects. The prerequisite is that the inventory is based on a clear and common ontology (e.g. for flat glass or other materials) that can function as a standard data collection layer.

Further, if the method for the scenarios where there is a BIM-model and where there is no BIM-model is standardized and made available, different actors such as architects, designers and planners can understand and use the information in a uniform way and implement it in their future projects by their BIM manuals and BIM coordination.

To enable replication, manuals for digitization, open “template files” where parameters are already linked to the ontology, and scripts or plugins that automatically transfer and structure information between different software (e.g. from point clouds or other software into BIM/Revit) would be needed.

LINKS

<https://www.demobv.nl/nl/re-suite>
<https://zenodo.org/>
<https://www.reincarnate-project.eu/>

CONTACTS

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